

The concept of obligation and its types in civil law

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Annotation: Norms of the law of obligations in terms of volume constitute a large part not only of the civil legislation, but also of the civil law system. Obligation law is one of the leading sub-fields of civil law, and it consists of relevant institutions and subsidiary institutions according to the characteristics of property relations regulated by its norms. This situation is related to the regulation of provision of various needs of individuals in many spheres of social life through the norms of the law of obligations.

The general rules of the law of obligations studied in this article apply to all types of obligations in the same way, therefore, these issues serve as a cornerstone in the special types of obligatory riyat, which are taught most often in the special part of civil law.

This article describes the concept, system and principles of the law of obligation.

Key words: Right of obligation, creditor, debtor, contractual obligation, non-contractual obligation, positive meaningful obligation, unilateral obligation, bilateral obligation, obligation to perform a specific action, alternative obligation, obligation with personal action, obligation without personal character.

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The law of obligation is the most important property relationship in our society important and wide field, in its civil-legal character rules. It also regulates relations between organizations and citizens, including relations that arise when selling various goods and food products to citizens, providing them with various services, providing housing, and in other cases.

Obligation is a civil legal relationship based on which one person (debtor) is forced to perform a certain action for the benefit of another person (creditor), such as: transfer property, perform work, provide services, pay money, etc , or refrain from a certain action, and the creditor has the right to require the debtor to fulfill his obligations.

In legal literature, together with the term obligation, the term duty is used. For example, the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan talks about rights and duties. These terms are synonymous, and the term obligation is always used in civil legal relations.

The law of obligation regulates the most important and broad field of property relations in society with its civil-legal rules. Legal relations regarding obligations in society are established for the purpose of satisfying and providing various needs of citizens and organizations. Norms on obligations regulate the transfer of property from one person to another, the provision of various services through production and household service enterprises. By means of obligations, the protection of property and property rights is ensured, damages caused to the citizen's health are compensated, etc.

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The system of obligation law consists of two main parts, i.e. general rules on obligations and special rules on specific types of obligations.

Legal institutions related to **contractual obligations** arise mainly from contractual relations, and its main feature is the manifestation of the will of the parties to the obligation.

Non-contractual obligations occur beyond the will of a person or result from a unilateral act.

In the general part of the law of obligation (Articles 234-385 of the Civil Code of Republic of Uzbekistan) origin and fulfillment of obligations, ensuring the fulfillment of obligations, the right to demand for transfer and transfer of debt, breach of obligations responsibility, grounds for cancellation of obligations, obligation the main legal instrument that creates relations estimated contracts and their conclusion, modification and cancellation tasks such as how to do it are determined.

The rights and obligations of the parties to each other are distinguished depending on their nature. They are divided into the following types depending on their content, objects and subjects:

1. Obligations with a positive meaning and obligations with a negative meaning. If the debtor is obliged to perform a specific action due to the obligation, and the creditor has the right to demand the performance of such an action, such an obligation is considered a positive obligation. Underlying most of the legal relationship are positive meaningful obligations. For example, obligations taken in

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the field of buying and selling, renting property, and providing household services are obligations with a positive meaning.

If the obligee is obligated to refrain from certain actions, and the creditor has the right to demand that he refrain from actions, such an obligation is considered a negative obligation. For example, if the author undertakes under the publishing contract to refrain from handing over his work to another publisher during the period of the contract, the publisher has the right to demand that the author refrain from entering into a contract with another publisher.

2. Unilateral and bilateral obligations. If one of the participants in the obligation has only the right (or rights) to demand, and the other party has only the obligation (obligations), such obligations are considered unilateral obligations. For example, a loan agreement. If the lender has the right to demand the repayment of the loan under the loan agreement, the debtor is obliged to repay the loan.

If each of the participants in the legal relationship has both a right and an obligation (a number of rights and obligations), such obligations are considered a bilateral obligation. Examples of bilateral obligations include sales, leases, and contracts. For example, in connection with a sale, the seller has the obligation to deliver the sold item, the recipient has the obligation to pay a fee corresponding to the value of the purchased item, and vice versa. Most obligations are bilateral obligations.

3. Obligations aimed at performing a specific action and alternative obligations. If, according to the legal relationship, the creditor has the right to demand a specific action from the debtor, for example, the performance of certain

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work, the delivery of any item, or the payment of a certain amount of money, such an obligation is an obligation aimed at the performance of a certain action. If in a legal relationship the debtor is obliged to perform one of several actions at the request of the creditor, such an obligation is considered an alternative obligation.

Even if several actions are indicated in the legal relationship regarding alternative obligation, the essence of the obligation is only one obligation of the debtor and the right of the creditor to demand the fulfillment of this obligation.

4. Personal obligations and non-personal obligations. Some obligations may be strictly related to the personality of each or one of the participants in the legal relationship. For example, the obligation arising under the contract of assignment is determined depending on whether the representative (performer of the assignment) is a trusted person. It is not allowed to transfer the fulfillment of obligations of such a personal nature to another person, unless otherwise stipulated by the law or contract, and the creditor cannot be exchanged with another person. Such obligations are usually canceled upon the death of the debtor or creditor.

In conclusion, the content of the obligations may include the rights aimed at demanding the performance of any property and non-property actions that do not violate the law, and the obligations received in connection with the performance of these actions.

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